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Research Article

**A COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE USEFULNESS OF
CONTAMINATION PROCEDURES WITH RESISTANT
DISTINCTIVENESS AND VULNERABILITY PATTERN**¹Dr. Muhammad Muaz Ul Hassan, ²Dr. Muhammad Shahid Ali, ³Dr. Muhammad Sultan Bashir
¹Sahiwal Medical College, Sahiwal**Abstract:**

Objectives: The main objective of the study was to find out the usefulness of simple control procedures on the contamination. It also includes the distinctiveness of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* including vulnerability patterns among health professionals and patients in coaching clinics.

Methods: Study was arranged from September 2016 to August 2017. It was a collaborative study conducted on patients selected from Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. Patient's samples were collected before and after one month of accomplishment of management procedures for outburst avoidance of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. These samples of patients were experienced for traditions and anti-microbial vulnerability. Data had been collected for methicillin-resistant and methicillin receptive *Staphylococcus aureus* infections, specialities of infection, and propensity patterns. After collecting these samples, it was determined that to what extent the simple control measures were successful. For a collection of mathematical data, SPSS was used.

Result: Total 390 patients were isolated for examination. From these 390, 180 were *Staphylococcus aureus*, 77 from healthcare personals and 103 from patients. Out of these patients, the number of methicillin-sensitive patients were 164 and methicillin-resistant 16. Some patients were well again from infections or crust and squasy tissues. Among the patients who were improved, 38 were methicillin-responsive and 8 were methicillin-resistant. The second most familiar source was the seepage which was predictable in 13.1% in methicillin-receptive and 1.6% in methicillin-defiant patients. In methicillin-resistant patients, 0% was defiant to Linezolid. Whereas all patients were defiant to Oxacillin, Cefoxitin, Amoxicillin, Cefotaxime and Cephradine. 87.7% were those patients who were defiant to both Co-Amoxiclav and Ciprofloxacin. The number of methicillin-defiant was lessened from 4 and 7 to 1 and 5 respectively when they were again examined after one month of accomplishment of effective control measures.

Conclusion: It has been concluded from the study that methicillin-responsive and methicillin-resistant differed from each other on the basis of anti-microbial receptiveness profiles. Antibiotics should be chosen on the basis of vulnerability and culture. Because of these control measurements, preclusion and cure of disease are possible. With the implementation of a control measure, a decreasing number of patients were observed in methicillin-defiant patients.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus Aureus*, Methicillin Resistant, Susceptible, Hospitals, Acquired Infections.

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INTRODUCTION:

Staphylococcus aureus is most common in the outer covering of skin and frontal nares. It is present in 80 % of hale and hearty persons. Mostly it causes the infections in skin and supple tissues. Other than this, it may cause nosocomial infections and can generate pneumonia, septic arthritis, endocarditis, and osteomyelitis.

The mortality rate of human beings was more than 80 % due to infections of *S. aureus* before the discovery of antibiotics. When the first antibiotic penicillin was discovered mortality, rate reduced to a large extent. This blond period was soon brought down by the initiation of penicillinase-producing SA strains. This SA strain was spread in the whole community and clinics. In early eighteen century, these defiant strains replaced the penicillin-susceptible strains. And soon these stains become the most widespread strains. In 60s Methicillin was introduced for the first time. It was a helpful drug in opposition to the penicillin producing strains. It has become the most favourite choice for treating SA infections. These strains were named Methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*. In 1961, in England, the first acknowledged case of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* was practised. These MRSA stains soon become popular in the entire world. In some countries of the world, health care linked MRSA is more widespread then HA-MRSA. In another way, community-linked MRSA is also becoming popular in many parts of the world. Health care problems caused by these infections are higher in emergent countries.

In the last few years, it has been observed that MRSA is spreading on a large scale. So, it has become a widespread cause of disease pervasiveness and infection in a population. Data together about the prevalence of MRSA in Pakistan is also dangerous. The smaller number of resources in progressing countries like Pakistan such as microbiology laboratories causing the prevalence of MRSA which is overwhelming. Physical contact is the main reason for the spread of MRSA. There is too much cruelty of unfettered antibiotics in Indian subcontinent where there is a huge number of communities. These antibiotics are also used for domestic animals and rooster industries. This has provided the ideal situation for the expansion of drug defiant in the population.

MRSA strains that cause the major infectious disease in the community include CC5, CC8, CC22, CC30 and CC45. There is a strong link between some strains and genes for pathogenesis. For Example, Sea, sek genes in ST239 strain and seg, sei, sem genes in

ST5 strain. Most skin and spongy tissues diseases in the United States are mostly caused by MRSA USA300. The occurrence of HA-MRSA and CA-MRSA has not been acknowledged well in Pakistan. There is a very little knowledge about the most recent HA-MRSA infections in hospitals of Peshawar. There is a stern devotion to simple control measures like general hand hygienic was accomplished after a current twine of MRSA-positive casa at the hospitals. However, there was no device to evaluate contagion category. This study was arranged to find out the category of the infection and distinctiveness of the patients of SA and healthcare personnel.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

The study was arranged from September 2016 to August 2017. It was a collaborative study conducted on patients selected from Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. After the endorsement from the institutional principles team and on paper informed permission from the matter, the samples were taken for the observations. The samples were collected after and before one month of control measurement treatment to seek the difference between them. Samples were gathered from various methods such as through swabs, seepage, tissue/abrasion, urine/catheter and respiratory suction equipment. These apparatuses were labelled and protected for MSSA, MRSA and anti-microbial receptiveness. According to the Centre for Disease Control (CDC) guidelines, segregation of SA, MRSA transmission and anti-microbial receptiveness outline was done. All this happened in the Pathology section of the hospital. Mannitol-Salt Agar was used for the injection of the sample, SA was recognized by the method of gram staining and various biochemical tests were done such as catalase, coagulase and deoxyribonuclease. Oxacillin is used instead of Methicillin because oxacillin is not available commercially. CDC average necessitates that since oxacillin disk dispersion alone is not steadfast, Cefoxitin should be used as a substitute for disk dispersion testing. Segregates presenting enlargement on this were labelled as MRSA. To assess receptiveness patterns of the segregates against frequently used antibiotics, Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion was used. The results collected after the experiment was broken up by measuring the zone of reticence according to the guidance of standard guideline.

Data was articulated as average, proportion, and standard deviation. It was analyzed by using SPSS. Microsoft Excel was used to formulate a bar chart of MRSA vulnerability to express the data in the more understandable form.

RESULTS:

Total 390 samples of data which were collected. Out of these total numbers 139 belongs to healthcare and 251 were linked to patients. For the care of patients belonging to healthcare, there were 74 doctors, 38 nurses, and 27 other team members. Among this entire staff, the numbers of females were 63 and there were 76 males. The average age limit was 29.58-7.326. The most frequently used method for collection of samples was nasal swabs about 75.5%. In 121 patients, it was also observed that microorganism's growth takes place. In 77 patients, SA bacterium was observed which was a most common bacterium. In this bacterium, gram-positive and gram-negative bacterium were also detected. The numbers of the gram-positive bacterium were 121 and 18 were gram negative. In addition, it was seen that 117 were vulnerable to Oxacillin and 4 were opposed to it. While 18 segregates cannot be differentiated that whether they were Oxacillin vulnerable or resistant. Similarly, these were isolated for Cefoxitin vulnerability or resistance. 117 were vulnerable to Cefoxitin, 4 were opposed to it and 18 were those whose prototype cannot be illustrious. MRSA isolates which were observed were only 4. 62 isolates cannot be eminent whether they were MSSA or MRSA. The class of disorder carried through the nose was 4.

Among the total 251 patients, some were collected before and some after the completion of control measures. About 65 patients were collected prior and 186 subsequent to the control measures. Patients consist of 129 females and 122 males. Average ages of the patients were 40.5-14.39 years. Most frequently used sample source was in patients 175. The most common procedure for the gathering of the sample was tissue/wound 106. In 225 samples of patient's bacterial growth was observed. The most familiar type of bacterium observed during the study was SA. Out of all these microbes observed, 113 were gram-positive, 122 were gram-negative and 26 were those whose status was not well known whether they are gram positive or gram negative. Moreover,

115 were disposed to Oxacillin, 69 were defiant to it and in 67 there were no distinguishing features can be observed. In the same way, 90 were vulnerable to Cefoxitin, 100 were defiant to it 61 specific prototypes could not be applied. In the sample group, 91 isolates were MSSA, 12 were MRSA and 148 could not be classified into MRSA or MSSA. The status for the nasal carrier was just 4.

A contour about the Anti-microbial propensity was generated. From the total 390 specimens, 180 were SA isolates. These isolates consist of 77 from health care workers and 103 from the patient. 164 isolates were from MSSA. There were no isolates found to be opposed to of Oxacillin and Cefoxitin. The high ratio of opposition was found for Amoxicillin and Co-Amoxiclav 141 both.

In addition, MRSA resistant isolates were 16 in number. While all isolates were against the Oxacillin, Cefoxitin, Amoxicillin, Cefotaxime and Cephadrine. 0 percent opposition was found against the Linezolid which was minimum of all. Opposition against Amoxiclav was 14, 1 against Vancomycin and 2 against Trimethoprim Sulpha Meth oxazole (TMP-SMX).

If we talk about the efficiency of the management measure, MRSA showing prior to the completion of control measures exposed an MRSA prevalence of 4 among healthcare staff with 73 subjects being MSSA. A great difference was observed after one month of control measures. MRSA position was lessened to 1 while MSSA subjects rising to 76.

Prior to the accomplishment of the management measures, MRSA spreading was 7, 23 MSSA, while some patients were found to have other bacterial infections whose number was about 35. A clear change was observed after the completion of control measures for one month, MRSA status was lessened to about 5, MSSA rising to 68 and other bacterial infections also increased to about 113.

Table – I: Source, Type++, Susceptibility and Status Stratification

Outcomes		Percentage
Source	Nasal Swab	105
	Ear Swab	32
	Pus	2
Type++	S. Aureus	77
	Staph. Epidermids	44
	No Growth	18
Susceptibility	Oxacillin	117
	Cefoxitin	117
Status	MSSA	73
	MRSA	4

Table – II: Source, Site, Bacteria and Status Stratification

Outcomes		Percentage
Source	In-patients	175
	Surgical ICU	39
	Post Discharge	37
Site Status	Tissue/Wound	106
	Puss	95
	Urine Catheter	20
	Suction Apparatus	8
	Swabs	22
Bacteria	A. Aureus	102
	E. Coli	48
	Pseudomonas A.	56
	Strep. Group	6
	Other Bacteria	13
	No Growth	26
Status	MSSA	91
	MRSA	12

Table – III: Antibiotics Stratification

Oxa	Cefo	Amox	Co-A	Cipro	Erythro	Genta	Calinda	Tetra	TMPSMX
0	0	86	86	43.9	25	4.3	10.4	37.8	20.7

Table – IV: Percentage of Antibiotics

Antibiotics	Percentage
Oxacillin	100
Cefoxitin	100
Amoxicillin	100
Co-Amox	87.5
Cefotaxime	100
Cephradine	100
Chloramphenicol	37.5
Ciprofloxacin	87.5
Levofloxacin	56.3
Norfloxacin	68.8
Ofloxacin	56.3
Sparfloxacin	37.5
Erythromycin	43.8
Gentamycin	56.3
Clindamycin	37.5
Doxycycline	62.5
Tetracyclin	62.5
Vancomycin	6.3
Linezolid	0
TMP-SMX	12.4

DISCUSSION:

It was observed from the study that *S. aureus* is responsible for such type of disorders. It is a saddle in recent healthcare with increasing occurrence and dominance. In 1989, the first case of MRSA was observed in Pakistan. A study was organized in 2013 according to which the occurrence of MRSA in Pakistan was 68.1%. It is reported that in Pakistan MRSA could be greatest to 42% and lowest to 7.5%. According to the results of the one study, three successive experiments performed on MRSA for their specific position. These tests reduced their commonness from 41.9% with disc dispersion to 38.1% with least inhibitory deliberation to only 27.9% with *mecA* gene recognition. According to study from a total of 390 healthcare staff, 16 were patients of MRSA-positive. Due to deficiency of proper manage measures, mistreat of antibiotics and lack of supervision, it is wide spreading day by day in Pakistan.

In our training hospitals, an MRSA-positive case was newly followed by an MRSA outburst. After that MRSA outburst measures were applied. These measures consist of simple control measures like firmly follow the cleanliness of hands, separation from other individuals and cohort. This was all done from September 2013 to January 2014. During the phase of 120 days in study units, 180 patients suffering from SA were recognized. These include 77 from healthcare staff and 103 from normal patients. The most important reason for nosocomial infection is the Hospital-acquired SA infections. According to study reports, it is 20 percent. It ascribed 153 cases according to our revision. These were the cases tainted after their admissions with ethnicity positive SA. 8 patients were male and 8 were females out of the entire MRSA patients. It was also notified in the earlier studies that sexual category of the persons is not a precisely essential aspect. There were no age limits in both MRSA and MSSA isolates. Mostly persons with an age group of 40 or less were affected. Therefore, old age was not a precisely important aspect in our study as mentioned earlier.

Isolates were tested for congeal status. In a preceding study, 70% were coalescing positive and 30% were coalescing negative. According to our study which was specifically on Staphylococci, we originate this to be 77 and 44 between healthcare staff, correspondingly. It was also observed among patients, that was 102 and 1 correspondingly. In patients, the mainstream of the bacteria, that were not congealed positive belonged to non-staphylococcus variety. Isolates were healthier from the abrasion site

in both the MSSA and MRSA. The MRSA isolates were 8 and that of MSSA were 38. The second most common source was Pus which was about 33. This observation is similar to the reported study where it was gash scrub 39.18% followed by seepage 20.94%. In our study mainly, the isolates were collected from the patients in SSTI. It was 46 which were also explained previously. In another study, it was observed that the, most widespread resource is respiratory infections. And according to another study, it was also demonstrated that the most frequent source for MRSA is urinary pathway infections which were 25.14%.

Special strains are related to different pathogenic genes. SasX plays its role in enhancing nasal colonization which was observed in a study. SesX is the surface-anchored protein. It was revealed that ST59-SCC was accountable for SSTIs. The study recommended that the exterior population was a considerable reservoir of MRSA or MSSA strains creating SSTIs that stumble on their way to hospitals. That's why conventional management strategies are not successful at preclusion of hospital-acquired transmissions. Therefore, new and modern health measures should be adapted to control MRSA outbursts that should prove helpful for the community.

For both the MRSA and MSSA, propensity sample for antibiotics was recognized. Maximum confrontation for MSSA isolates was found against Amoxicillin and Co-Amoxiclav which was 86% for both. It was also described in the previous study in which confrontation was 80.7% for Amoxicillin and 87.7% for penicillin. Opposition for other antibiotics such as Erythromycin, Gentamycin, Clindamycin, Tetracycline and Co-Trimoxazole was 30.5%, 1.56%, 13.9%, 31.25% and 27.7% correspondingly. According to our study results for antibiotic opposition were 25%, 4.3%, 10.4%, 37.8% and 20.7%, correspondingly. No opposition was found for two antibiotics in our study these were Oxacillin and Cefoxitin.

100 percent opposition was revealed against Amoxicillin, penicillin and Oxacillin among the MRSA isolates. We recognized 100% MRSA opposition against Oxacillin, Cefoxitin, Amoxicillin, Cephotaxime and Cephradine. The minimum opposing drug was found to be Vancomycin. These observations were similar to our study. In our study resistant against Vancomycin was 6.3%. However, in our study, a drug was found to be less resistant than Vancomycin. It was Linezolid whose resistance was

0%. Similarly, MRSA resistance was found to be 59.16%, 70.15%, 74%, 69.10%, 67.01%, for Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Ofloxacin, Erythromycin and Gentamycin correspondingly, according to one study. In another study, these resistances were found to be 44.59%, 80.40%, 70%, 85.81% and 76.35% respectively. And these ratios were 87.5%, 56.3%, 43.8% and 56.3% correspondingly, according to our study. Another study revealed that MRSA opposition to Co-Trimoxazole was 86.48% which was 11% according to observations of our study.

The control measures which enforced include liquid hand washing and wipes with surface active disease controlling chemicals. In surface active antiseptics the most commonly used is Chlorhexidine. However, the opposition was observed. Resistance was observed in two cases of MRSA between the healthcare staff such as medical staff in our study. Excessive uses of antiseptics cause the initiation of MRSA strains. It also lessens the inclination of antiseptics. Another antiseptic Mupirocin controlled the Hospital gained resettlement and contamination. However, later on, it was also reported that Mupirocin confrontation is also pragmatic.

In our study, the rate of MRSA contagion among healthcare staff was condensed from 4 to 1 after one month of control treatment. Regardless of the simple control measure, MRSA exemption theme was recommended for a further cure. This reduction in MRSA infection was replaced with the colonization of MSSA among the subjects in healthcare staff. As a consequence, the MSSA colonization increased from 73 to 76. After the control measure treatment in patients for one month, MRSA infection decreased from 7 to 5. It is also notable that before the implementation of control measures, the number of 7 was from a total of 65 patients. On the other way after the control measure treatment number was 5 from 186 patients. This reveals that the chances of MRSA among patients decreased to highest rate after the one-month treatment of control measures.

This study shows that the MRSA infections between healthcare staff and patients were intermittent because of execution of control measures. This study showing 0.7% and 2.7% chances of the total samples in their own groups, which were 2.9% and 10.8% before the control measures. MRSA segregates were defiant to Co-Amoxiclav and quinolones but were disposed to Linezolid, Vancomycin and Co-Trimoxazole. This reflects the importance of appropriate medley of antibiotics. Antibiotics should be chosen on the basis of culture and compassion. So that they could decrease the puddle of drug opposing

bacteria. At last, it is significant to identify the resistance against Mupirocin by further studies on it. So that it could make effective to control the MRSA and Staphylococcus aureus.

CONCLUSION:

The execution of control measures was greatly helpful against MRSA infections. To find out the usefulness of these control measures and to verify the extent of colonization and propagation of MRSA to hospitalized patients and healthcare staff, further studies should be organized.

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